

BIM QA/QC PROCEDURES BASED ON LESSONS LEARNED FROM CONSTRUCTABILITY ISSUES

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Abstract

The Architecture, Engineering, and Construction Industry is a competitive market where having strategies that improve the quality of the construction buildings is a valuable investment. Quality is an extensive concept that addresses the compliance and satisfaction between the requested job and the delivered project.

This study focuses on applying constructability as a quality technique that improves the deliverables between the construction and the design teams in a Design-Build company with the objective of cross-learning between projects. It proposes the use of Building Information Modelling (BIM) to facilitate the integration of the construction knowledge while developing a construction project.

The thesis includes the design and detail of a framework using BIM to collect, analyse, store, communicate, and use/reuse the construction knowledge contained in the Request for Information (RFI) and the Redlines of a project when the construction team and the design team interacts.

While performing the case study, a series of tools were implemented, such as a digitalized RFI and Redlines formats, constructability classification system, constructability knowledge database relational diagram, and constructability quality checklists that can be easily integrated in the existing QA/QC procedures of a construction company.

Dissertation:

<https://bimaplus.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/2020-AnaLuna-Dissertation.pdf>

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/H7r-ir05ZA4>

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